

Country	Institutions
United States	Carnegie Mellon University, Georgia Institute of Technology, East Tennessee State University, Syracuse University, Harvard University, University of Maryland, PARC, University of Washington, Northeastern University, Partnership on AI, IBM Research, Winthrop University, Stanford University, Cornell University, North Carolina State University, University of Minnesota, The City University of New York, Microsoft Research
Germany	University of Stuttgart, Leibniz University Hannover, Technical University of Munich, HTW Berlin, RTPU - University of Kaiserslautern-Landau, Volkswagen Group
Australia	University of Technology Sydney (UTS), Curtin University, Monash University, Australian National University, University of New South Wales, CSIRO
Netherlands	University of Twente, Strategic Analysis and Policy Department, Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek (TNO), HU University of Applied Sciences Utrecht, Delft University of Technology
United Kingdom	University of Oxford, Imperial College London, University of Bristol, Human Centred Futures, London
Brazil	University of Brasilia (UnB), SENAI CIMATEC University Center, PUC-Rio, FGV
Canada	National Research Council Canada, Naval Postgraduate School, Mila - Quebec AI Institute, University of Toronto
Finland	University of Jyväskylä, University of Oulu, Laurea University of Applied Sciences
Austria	Graz University of Technology, Vienna University of Economics and Business
India	Department of Information Technology Ajay Kumar Garg Engineering College, National Institute of Technology Patna
Ireland	Trinity College Dublin, University College Cork
Italy	University of Bari "A. Moro", Scuola Normale Superiore
Bulgaria	National Academy of Arts
China	Southern University of Science and Technology
Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology
South Korea	Sungkyunkwan University
Denmark	University of Copenhagen
Spain	Artificial Intelligence Research Institute (IIIA-CSIC)
France	Université de Lorraine
Malaysia	Universiti Malaya
Malta	University of Malta
Norway	Equality and Anti-discrimination Ombud
Qatar	Hamad Bin Khalifa University

Singapore	Salesforce Research
Sweden	Umeå University
Switzerland	University of St. Gallen